

USING INNOVATIVE TOOLS AND METHODS TO DELIVER LESSONS PRODUCTIVELY

**Muratova Marfa,
Tongotarova Gulchehra,
Barnoyev Jahongir**

Annotation: Using innovative methods of teaching is a crucial skill for teachers and education staff. Scientific research has shown that innovative teaching methods and approaches can significantly enhance the student learning process. However, experimenting new methods and strategies we can improve student engagement and attainment and is a win-win for both students and teachers. In this paper we have to discuss about innovative teaching methods and strategies.

Key words: Innovative teaching method, Innovative Strategies for teaching, Teaching strategies in classroom

Some of our most inspiring and unforgettable movies are of teachers and professors who use innovative methods of teaching to reach out to the minds of the students and win the hearts of the audience while doing so. While a few years ago, one would only see such innovative and effective teaching on the screen, today technology has given teachers across the world a number of tools to enhance teaching methods. Here are some innovative teaching strategies which every teacher can embrace and make their teaching way more interesting:

1. Cross over Teaching

While this form of teaching does not include technology, it is an enriching experience for the student as well as the faculty. Here, the learning happens in an informal setting such as after-school learning clubs, or trips to museums and exhibition. The teacher can link the educational content with the experiences that the students are having. This teaching is further enhanced and deepened by adding

questions related to the subject. The students can then add to the classroom discussions through field trip notes, photographic projects and other group assignments related to the trip.

2. Teaching through Smart Boards

Smart boards are an effective way to bring the classroom to life while helping students experience a deeper level of engagement and understanding. This is done by making the course content interactive and visual. The smart boards transform the teaching experience into an interactive and collaborative experience as the teachers use dynamic multimedia content, to help convey the topic more effectively to the students and making it a visual, engaging experience.

3. Teaching through Flipping Classrooms

Flipping the classroom is becoming an increasingly popular effective teaching method. In this technique, the students are made active participants of the learning process by passing the onus of learning on them, it requires the teachers to relegate to the role of resource providers and the students take the responsibility of gathering concepts information. Using various tools of technology the students are encouraged to constructing knowledge, fill in the information gaps and make inferences on their own as and when needed. While many may question if giving students the responsibility of learning may work, it has been seen by teachers across the world that when put in charge of their own learning they immerse themselves more in the subject, taking more interest and learning better. This method of teaching is one of the best ways to lay the foundation in independent learning.

4. Teaching through collaboration

Another innovative method of teaching involves encouraging student collaboration for various projects. Today, we live in a globalized world and collaboration is an essential life skill that is important for all careers and enterprises. Teachers can help foster this skill in the classroom by allowing students to learn, study and work in groups. For instance, by assigning group homework or encouraging students to work

together on plays, presentations and other reports. Today, collaboration as a form of teaching is gaining acceptance as a powerful teaching tool where once again the responsibility is on the group of students are the educators play to the role of guides, mentors, supervisors for the students. It also teaches students empathy, negotiation skills, teamwork, and problem-solving.

5. Teaching through Virtual Reality

Virtual Reality technology involves helping students learn through interactions with a 3D world. For instance, instead of taking the students through a boring history class, the teachers can use 3D technology to explore ancient civilizations, travel to distant countries for a class in geography or even take a trip to outer space during a class on science.

6. Teaching through 3D printing technology

Teachers looking for innovative methods of teaching can also look at 3D printing as a means of teaching. This method is fast gaining global acceptance, especially in higher educational institutes where 3D printers are used to create prototypes and make complex concepts easy to understand. In the lower level classrooms, teachers can use the 3D printers to teach content that was previously taught via textbooks, thus helping students gain a better understanding of the concept- especially STEM subjects.

8. Technology and innovative methods of teaching

The use of technology in the classroom helps to engage the students with different kinds of stimuli and creates an environment of activity-based learning. It makes the content of the classroom more interesting and makes learning fun.

For teachers, technology offers an endless set of resources that they can tap into depending on the need of the students. While this blog lists a few such resources, for a teacher looking for effective teaching methods in a classroom, turning towards the latest technology will offer a vast number of updated solutions.

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